

Synthesis, spectral characterization and biological screening of a tetraaza-macrocyclic ligand and its complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}

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Abstract : Complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) with a 12-membered 1,3,7,9-tetraaza-4,6,10,12-tetraphenyl-2,8-diketocyclododecane macrocyclic ligand (L) have been synthesized. These complexes are characterized by the elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, mass, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies.

All the complexes are non electrolytes so they may be formulated as [M(L)X₂] [where, M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and X = Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻]. On the basis of IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies an octahedral geometry has been assigned for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes and tetragonal geometry for Cu^{II} complexes. The antimicrobial activities of the ligand and its complexes, as growth inhibiting agents have been screened *in vitro* against different species of bacteria and pathogenic fungi.

Keywords : Cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), tetraazamacrocyclic ligand, complex.

Introduction

The intense interest in synthetic macrocycles and their metal complexes depends on the fact that they mimic naturally occurring macrocyclic molecules in their structural and functional features due to rich chemical properties¹⁻⁴. One of these properties is the enhanced thermo-

for metal ions⁹⁻¹². In this paper, we report the spectral studies on Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with a new tetraazamacrocyclic ligand (Fig. 1). On the basis of analytical, magnetic and spectral data, an octahedral geometry for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} while tetragonal geometry for Cu^{II} complexes has been assigned.

Fig. 1. Preparation and structure of the ligand (L).

chemical and kinetic stability of the complexes with regard to their dissociation, that is a lesser lability and larger association constants than the complexes with homologous open-chain chelating ligands. The application of polyazamacrocyclic precursors in the synthesis of transition metal macrocyclic complexes stems mainly from their use as models for protein-metal binding sites in biological systems⁵⁻⁸ and as selective complexing agents

Results and discussion

The formation of the ligand and the complexes may be represented by the following reactions :

On the basis of elemental analysis, the complexes were

Table 1. Molar conductance and elemental analysis data of the complexes

Complex	MW (Calcd.)	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
					Found (Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	M
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	626	Pink	272	60	61.28 (61.34)	3.91 (3.83)	8.82 (8.95)	9.53 (9.41)
C ₃₂ H ₂₄ CoN ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂								
[Co(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	679	Dark pink	264	55	56.72 (56.55)	3.45 (3.53)	12.43 (12.37)	8.56 (8.67)
C ₃₂ H ₂₄ CoN ₆ O ₈								
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	626	Light green	284	65	61.47 (61.34)	3.72 (3.83)	8.89 (8.95)	9.47 (9.38)
C ₃₂ H ₂₄ NiN ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂								
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	679	Light green	270	68	56.63 (56.55)	3.62 (3.53)	12.50 (12.37)	8.53 (8.65)
C ₃₂ H ₂₄ NiN ₆ O ₈								
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	631	Green	> 300	65	60.75 (60.86)	3.73 (3.80)	8.94 (8.87)	9.97 (10.06)
C ₃₂ H ₂₄ CuN ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂								
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	684	Green	292	62	56.22 (56.14)	3.45 (3.51)	12.19 (12.28)	9.38 (9.28)
C ₃₂ H ₂₄ CuN ₆ O ₈								

found to have the composition as shown in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO is corresponding to nonelectrolyte nature. These complexes may be formulated as [M(L)X₂] [where, M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and X = Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻]. The electron impact mass spectrum of metal free ligand (L), (Fig. 2) confirms the proposed formula by showing a peak at 518

The IR spectrum of ligand (L) does not show any band corresponding to a free primary diamine and keto group. The main characteristic strong band appeared at 1597 cm⁻¹ corresponding to >C=N. This band confirms the reaction between amide -NH₂ group of urea and carbonyl groups of the diketone. So, the bands due to -NH₂ group of urea in 3200-3350 cm⁻¹ region and >C=O group of carbonyl compounds above 1700 cm⁻¹ are ab-

Fig. 2. Electron-impact mass spectra of the ligand (L).

amu (i.e. atomic mass 496 corresponding to the macrocyclic moiety (C₃₂H₂₄N₄O₂) + 23 atomic mass of Na⁺ ion). It also shows a series of peaks i.e. 194, 222, 232, 275, 293, 316, 374 and 467 amu, etc. corresponding to various fragments. Their intensity conveys the idea of the stability of fragments.

This confirms the elimination of water molecules and also the complete condensation. The bands at 754 cm⁻¹ and 1464 cm⁻¹ are due to the presence of phenyl rings in the macrocycle. The bands corresponding to ν(M-N) and ν(M-Cl) are appeared at 465-470 and 365-370 cm⁻¹ respectively which indicates the involvement of

N and Cl in coordination.

IR spectra of the complexes : The presence of the absorption bands at 1435–1458, $\nu(\text{N}=\text{O})$ 1307–1318 and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$ 1001–1069 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of the nitrate complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} suggest that both the nitrate groups are coordinated to the central metal ion in a unidentate fashion^{14–16}.

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis (Table 1). The higher melting points of the metal complexes than the ligand indicate their high thermal stability.

Cobalt(II) complexes : At room temperature the magnetic moment of Co^{II} complexes lies in the range 4.82–4.99 B.M. corresponding to three unpaired electrons (Table 2). The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes display three absorption bands in the range 10330–10638,

Table 2. Magnetic moment and electronic spectral data of the complexes

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	4.82	10638, 14684, 18621
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	4.99	10330, 14577, 18621
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	3.00	11223, 16155, 28011
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	2.85	13280, 18621, 28490
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	1.97	10224, 18621, 25706
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	2.04	10266, 18621, 28571

14577–14684, 18621 cm^{-1} . These bands may be assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively¹⁸. The position of these bands suggests an octahedral environment around the Co^{II} ion^{16,17} (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Suggested structure of the complexes where $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and $X = \text{Cl}^-$ and NO_3^- .

The EPR spectra of the Co^{II} complexes were recorded in polycrystalline matrix and in DMSO solution at liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT). The g -values were found to

be almost the same in both the cases (Table 3). It indicates that the complexes have the same geometry in the solid as well as in solution.

Table 3. EPR spectral data of the complexes

Complex	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}	G
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	2.0446	2.0255	2.0319	-
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	2.0839	2.0575	2.0663	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	2.1480	2.0445	2.0786	3.3258
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	2.3651	2.1412	2.2157	2.5856

Nickel(II) complexes : Magnetic moment of Ni^{II} complexes at room temperature lies in the range 2.85–3.00 B.M. (Table 2). These values are in tune with a high spin configuration and show the presence of an octahedral environment around the Ni^{II} ion in the complexes. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show bands in the range 11223–13280, 16155–18621, 28011–28490 cm^{-1} characteristic to an octahedral geometry¹⁸. Thus, these bands may be assigned to the three spin allowed transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively.

Copper(II) complexes : The magnetic moment for Cu^{II} complexes lies in the range 1.97–2.04 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron (Table 2). The complexes may be considered to possess a tetragonal geometry. The electronic spectra of these complexes display bands in the range 10224–10266, 18621, 25706–28571 cm^{-1} . These bands correspond to the transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ (ν_1), $B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{zy}$) (ν_2) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{zy}, d_{y^2}$) (ν_3) respectively¹⁹.

EPR spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes were recorded at room temperature in polycrystalline matrix and in DMSO solution on X-band at frequency 9.5 GHz under the magnetic field strength 3000 G. Polycrystalline spectra shows a well-resolved anisotropic broad signal²⁰. The analysis of spectra give $g_{\parallel} = 2.1480$ – 2.3651 and $g_{\perp} = 2.0445$ – 2.1412 (Table 3). The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$, observed for the complexes indicate that the unpaired electron is localized in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the Cu^{II} ion and spectral features are characteristic for the axial symmetry. Tetragonally elongated structure is thus confirmed for the Cu^{II} complexes²¹.

$G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, which is the measurement of the exchange interaction between the metal centers in a solid sample of the complex has also been calculated. According to Hathway and Billing²², if $G > 4$, the exchange interaction is negligible but $G < 4$ indicates the

considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. The complexes reported here gives the 'G' value in the range 2.5856–3.3258, which is < 4 , indicating exchange interaction in the solid complexes.

Ligand field parameters : Various ligand field parameters were calculated for the complexes and are listed in the Table 4. The value of Dq in Co^{II} complexes were

Table 4. Ligand field parameters of complexes

Complex	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	LFSE (kJ mol^{-1})
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	1330	739	0.66	127
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	1285	714	0.64	123
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	1122	699	0.67	161
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	1328	485	0.47	191

calculated from transition energy ratio diagram using the ν_3/ν_2 ratio¹⁸. The Nephelauxetic parameter β was readily obtained by using the relation :

$\beta = B(\text{Complex})/B(\text{Free ion})$, where $B(\text{Free ion})$ for Co^{II} is 1120 cm^{-1} and for Ni^{II} is 1041 cm^{-1} ¹⁷. The values of β lie in the range of 0.47–0.67. These values indicate the appreciable covalent character of the metal ligand ' σ ' bond.

Biological study : The ligand (L) and its complexes were evaluated against different species of bacteria and fungi, (Graph 1) as per procedure reported earlier^{23–26}.

aureus (gram-negative) bacteria at $30 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The disc of Whatmann no. 1 filter paper having the diameter 5.00 mm were soaked in the solution of compounds in DMF (1.5 mg cm^{-1}). After drying, it was observed after 36 h. DMF was served as a control and *Streptomycin* as a standard drug. The zone of inhibition was calculated in mm and the growth inhibition capacity of the complexes follow the order : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$.

Antifungal screening : The antifungal activity of the ligand and its complexes was tested by the agar plate technique against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus glaucus* and *Aspergillus flavus*. The compounds were directly mixed to the medium in different concentrations. The fungus was placed on the medium with the help of inoculum needle in the centre of the petriplates. These treated petridishes were incubated at $30 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 72 to 96 h. The growth of fungus was measured diametrically and the growth inhibition was calculated by the following relation :

$$\text{Fungal growth inhibition \%} = \frac{(A - B) \times 100}{A}$$

where A is the diameter of the fungus in the control plate and B is the diameter of the fungus in the test plate.

The complexes show fungal inhibition in the following order : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$.

Graph 1. Biological screening data of the ligand (L) and complexes.

Antibacterial screening : The antibacterial activity of the ligand and the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} was tested by the disc diffusion technique against *Sarcina lutea* (gram-positive), *Escherchia coli* and *Staphylococcus*

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and procured from Sigma-Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received.

Synthesis of ligand : The hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of dibenzoylmethane (4.48 g, 0.02 mol) and hot aqua-ethanolic solution (20 mL) of urea (1.2 g, 0.02 mol) were mixed slowly with constant stirring. This mixture was refluxed at 75 °C for 7–8 h in presence of few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. On cooling, a solid white precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed with cold EtOH and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Yield 64%, m.p. 110 °C (Found C, 77.35; H, 4.76; N, 11.34. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₄N₄O₂ (atomic mass 496) : C, 77.42; H, 4.84; N, 11.29%).

Synthesis of complexes : The hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of ligand (0.496 g, 0.001 mol) and hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of corresponding metal salt (0.001 mol) were mixed together with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 5 to 7 h at 70 to 80 °C. On cooling a coloured precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed with cold EtOH and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

Physical measurements : The C, H and N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the ELICO (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CuSO₄·5H₂O as a calibrant. Electron impact mass spectra were recorded on TOF MS ES+ mass spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample and in the solution of DMSO, at liquid nitrogen temperature for Co^{II} and at room temperature for Cu^{II} complexes on E₄-EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as the g-marker.

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References

1. L. F. Lindoy, "The Chemistry of Macrocyclic Ligand Complexes", Cambridge University Press, UK, 1989.
2. P. Dietrich, P. Viout and J. M. Lehn, "Macrocyclic Chemistry", VCH Publishers Inc, New York, 1993.
3. R. M. Izatt, K. Powlak and J. S. Bradshaw, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **91**, 1721.
4. F. Lions, *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **19**, 177.
5. E. Kimura, C. A. Dalimunte, A. Yamashita and R. Machida, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1985, 1041.
6. D. E. Fenton and H. Okawa, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 1349.
7. E. Kimura, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1993, **65**, 355.
8. K. D. Karlin and Z. Tyeklar, "Bioinorganic Chemistry of Copper", Chapman and Hall, New York, 1991.
9. H. F. Handel, R. Muller and R. Guglielmetti, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **66**, 514.
10. H. Tsubuke, T. Yoden, T. Iwachido and M. Zenki, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 1069.
11. M. K. Beklemishev, S. Elshani and C. M. Wai, *Anal. Chem.*, 1994, **66**, 3521.
12. B. S. Mohite, D. N. Zambare and B. E. Mahadik, *Anal. Chem.*, 1994, **66**, 4097.
13. S. Chandra and K. Gupta, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 329.
14. S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2004, **60A**, 2767.
15. S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2004, **60A**, 3079; C. R. K. Rao and P. S. Zacharias, *Polyhedron*, 1977, **16**, 1201.
16. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970.
17. S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **7**, 243.
18. A. B. P. Lever, "Crystal Field Spectra. Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 1st ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
19. V. V. Pavlishchuk, S. P. Kolotilov, A. W. Addison, R. J. Butcher and E. Sinn, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 335.
20. S. Chandra, K. Gupta and S. Sharma, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 1205.
21. B. Jezowska, J. Lisowski, A. Vogt and P. Chmielewski, *Polyhedron*, 1988, **7**, 337.
22. B. J. Hathaway and D. E. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 143; R. J. Dudley and B. J. Hathaway, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 1725.
23. S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2004, **60A**, 1563.
24. S. Chandra, L. K. Gupta and Sangeetika, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2004, **34**, 1591.
25. A. Bansai and R. V. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 989.
26. W. G. Hanna and M. M. Moawad, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 644.